

Metal-rich metallaboranes: Synthesis and structure of *nido*-[(Cp*Rh)₃B₆H₈(μ-CO)][†]

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This work reports the results of a thermally driven cluster expansion reaction of [(Cp*Rh)₂B₃H₇] (Cp* = η⁵-C₅Me₅), *nido*-**1** with metal carbonyl compounds. In addition to the previously reported products, the reactivity of *nido*-**1** with [Mn₂(CO)₁₀] led to the isolation of a new rhodaborane cluster [(Cp*Rh)₃B₆H₈CO], **4**, in modest yield. Electron counting rules predict the geometry of **4** to be a *nido*-rhodaborane having a core similar to a decaborane with one vertex missing. These predictions were further confirmed experimentally by spectroscopic characterization in solution and structure determinations in the solid state. On the other hand, the reaction of *nido*-**1** with [Fe₂(CO)₉] yielded a trinuclear metal carbonyl cluster [(Cp*Rh){Fe(CO)₃}{Fe(CO)₄}(μ-CO)₂], **7**. Both compounds **4** and **7** have been characterized in solution by IR, ¹H, ¹¹B NMR and mass spectrometry and the structural types were unequivocally established by crystallographic analysis.

Keywords: Boron, metallaborane, heterometallic, rhodium, rhodaborane, iron.

Introduction

Metallaborane chemistry which is an important part of polyhedral boron chemistry, is an gradually emerging field of study¹⁻⁴. The fascinating aspect of metallaborane chemistry is its close connection with organometallic chemistry¹⁻⁵. There is an ongoing interest in the synthesis of metallaborane compounds of novel geometry, and the important aspects of these studies have been the recognition of unique structural types^{2,6-9}. The electron-counting rules and the isolobal principle provide a basis for the understanding of the inter relationships between the structure and composition¹⁰. Metallaborane compounds can be arranged in two main areas: boron-rich^{1,3,5,7,11-16} and metal-rich metallaboranes¹⁷⁻¹⁹ with the majority being boron-rich metallaboranes. Metal-rich boron clusters are members of a rapidly growing family of metallaborane "hybrid" systems which bridges the gap between metal clusters and polyhedral boranes¹⁹. Alternatively, the development of heterometallic clusters has been noteworthy over the years²⁰. These heterometallic clusters are expected to provide different properties in comparison with those of homometallic complexes owing to their varied electronic interactions²¹. We, thus, shifted our focus towards the

synthesis of heterometallic metallaborane clusters²², made up of different transition metals of group 4-9.

In metallaborane chemistry, transition metal carbonyl compounds have received considerable attention in connection with their potential as versatile reagent in metal cluster building reactions^{23,24}. A combination of metal polychloride and borane reagents with metal carbonyl fragments results in metal fragment substitution, creating interesting cluster geometries^{25,26}. Having synthesized a wide range of metallaboranes containing group 4 to 9 transition metals²⁷⁻³⁰, a variety of reactivity patterns were investigated, and the reactions with metal carbonyls have been found to be the most successful for cluster expansion reaction as well as synthesis of metal borides^{18,29,30}. Earlier, we have reported a novel μ₉-boride cluster, generated from the reaction of an open cage rhodaborane [(Cp*Rh)₂B₆H₁₀] with [Co₂(CO)₈]³¹. Recently, we have isolated and structurally characterized two heterometallic μ₉-boride clusters [(Cp*Rh)₃(RhCO)₃-Fe(CO)₃(μ-CO)₃B₃H₂] and [(Cp*Rh)₃Rh(CO)₂(Mn(CO)₃)₂-B₄H₃] from the cluster expansion reaction of *nido*-**1** with Fe₂(CO)₉ and Mn₂(CO)₁₀ respectively^{31b}. After developing a fruitful synthetic route to heterometallic μ₉-boride clusters^{31,32}, we were interested in synthesizing analogous boride

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clusters with metal carbonyl fragments. The lack of mixed-metal boride clusters and the recent findings in group 9 metallaboranes of Rh^{32,33} using first row metal carbonyls, encouraged us to isolate mixed-metal boride clusters using other metal carbonyls. Although the objective of isolating different metal boride cluster was not achieved, our experimental efforts enabled us to isolate a *nido* cluster from cluster growth reaction with [Mn₂(CO)₁₀]. In this article, we present the results of the reaction between *nido-1* with various metal carbonyl fragments under different reaction conditions.

Experimental

General Procedures and Instrumentation

All the manipulations were conducted under an Ar/N₂ atmosphere using standard Schlenk techniques or glove box technique. Solvents were distilled prior to use under argon. Compound *nido-1* was synthesized using a literature method^{31c}, while other chemicals were obtained commercially and used as received. The external reference [Bu₄N][B₃H₈] for the ¹¹B NMR was synthesized with the literature method³⁴. Preparative thin layer chromatography was performed with Merck 105554 silica gel TLC plates. The NMR spectra were recorded on a 400 or 500 MHz Bruker FT-NMR spectrometer. Residual solvent protons were used as reference (δ , ppm C₆D₆, 7.15) and (δ , ppm CDCl₃, 7.26), while a sealed tube containing [Bu₄N(B₃H₈)] in [*d*₆]-benzene (δ_B , ppm, -30.07) was used as an external reference for the ¹¹B NMR. The FT-IR spectrum was recorded using a Jasco FT/IR-4100 spectrometer. HRMS (ESI) spectra were carried out using Qtof Micro YA263 HRMS instrument. Note that, all the reported compounds are isolated by preparative thin layer chromatographic technique (TLC) using silica gel coated aluminum TLC plates. The impure reaction mixture was slowly loaded on the TLC and eluted by using the hexane/CH₂Cl₂ mixture in inert atmosphere. Elution with particular solvent mixture allowed us to separate the compounds in pure form.

Synthesis of 4

In a flame dried Schlenk tube, *nido-1* (0.13 g, 0.25 mmol) and [Mn₂(CO)₁₀] (0.487 g, 1.25 mmol) were thermalized in toluene at 90°C for 12 h. The solvent was evaporated in vacuo; residue was extracted into hexane and passed through Celite. After removal of solvent, the residue was re-dissolved in CH₂Cl₂ solvent and slowly loaded on the preparative TLC plates (Merck 105554 silica gel TLC plates). Elution with

hexane/CH₂Cl₂ (80:20 v/v) solvent mixture in an inert atmosphere allowed us to separate the compound in pure form as purple **4** (0.010 g, 4%).

4: HRMS (ESI) Calcd. for C₃₁H₅₃B₆ORh₃Na⁺ [M+Na]⁺ *m/z* 839.1718, Found *m/z* 839.1726. ¹¹B{¹H} NMR (160 MHz, C₆D₆, 22°C): δ = 60.0 (s, 1B), 29.9 (s, 2B), 15.0 (s, 1B), 2.6 (s, 1B), -2.1 (s, 1B); ¹H NMR (500 MHz, C₆D₆, 22°C): δ = 4.64 (4H, BH_i), 2.88 (1H, BH_i), 2.51 (1H, BH_i), 2.06 (s, 15H, Cp*), 1.68 (s, 30H, Cp*), -2.87 (br, 1H, B-H-B), -13.59 (br, 1H, M-H-B); ¹³C{¹H} NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃, 22°C): δ = 186.7 (CO), 103.6, 102.5, (s, C₅Me₅), 8.02, 7.88 (s, C₅Me₅); IR (hexane, cm⁻¹): 2482 br, 2423 br (BH_i), 1734 s (CO).

Synthesis of 7

In a flame dried Schlenk tube, *nido-1* (0.13 g, 0.25 mmol) was stirred with [Fe₂(CO)₉] (0.491 g, 1.35 mmol) in hexane at room temperature for 12 h. The solvent was evaporated in vacuo, residue was extracted in hexane and passed through Celite. After removal of solvent, the residue was re-dissolved in CH₂Cl₂ solvent and slowly loaded on the preparative TLC plates (Merck 105554 silica gel TLC plates). Elution with hexane/CH₂Cl₂ (80:20 v/v) mixture in an inert atmosphere allowed us to separate the compound in pure form as green **7** (0.016, 10%).

7: HRMS (ESI) Calcd. for C₁₉H₁₅O₉Fe₂RhK⁺ [M+K]⁺ *m/z* 640.8107, Found *m/z* 640.8080. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃, 22°C): δ = 1.85 (s, 15H, Cp*); ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃, 22°C): δ = 216.7 (CO), 108.1 (s, C₅Me₅), 8.99 (s, C₅Me₅); IR (hexane, cm⁻¹): 2064 vs, 2015, 1962, 1844, 1797 vs. (terminal and bridging CO stretching).

X-Ray Structure Determination

The crystal data for **4** and **7** were collected and integrated using a Bruker Kappa apex2 CCD diffractometer, with graphite monochromated Mo-K α (λ = 0.71073 Å) radiation at 296 K. The structures were solved by heavy atom methods using SHELXS-2016/6 or SIR92 and refined using SHELXL-2016/6 (Sheldrick 2015, G.M., University of Göttingen)³⁵.

Crystal data for **4**: CCDC 1868811, C₃₁H₅₁B₆ORh₃, *M_r* = 813.30, Monoclinic, *P* 21/*n*, *a* = 8.4999(4) Å, *b* = 21.6471(9) Å, *c* = 21.3342(9) Å, *V* = 3925.4 Å³, *Z* = 4, $\rho_{\text{Calcd.}}$ = 1.376 mg/m³, μ = 1.267 mm⁻¹, *F*(000) = 1640, *R*1 = 0.0522, *wR*2 = 0.1286, 7499 independent reflections [$2\theta \leq 51.59^\circ$] and 484 parameters.

Crystal data for **7**: CCDC 1868812 C₁₉H₁₅Fe₂O₉Rh, *M_r* = 601.92, Orthorhombic, *P* 2ac 2ab, *a* = 9.7109(8) Å, *b* = 14.2848(11) Å, *c* = 15.1249(12) Å, *V* = 2098.1(3) Å³, *Z* = 4, ρ_{Calcd.} = 1.906 mg/m³, μ = 2.191 mm⁻¹, *F*(000) = 1192, *R*₁ = 0.0234, *wR*₂ = 0.0383, 5217 independent reflections [2θ ≤ 53.59°] and 285 parameters.

Results and discussion

Synthesis of rhodaborane 4: In an attempt to improve the yield of μ₉-boride cluster [(Cp*Rh)₃Rh(CO)₂(Mn(CO)₃)₂B₄H₃], **2**^{31b}, we explored the same reaction under different reaction conditions. As shown in Scheme 1, along with the formation of **2**, another product, [(Cp*Rh)₃B₆H₈CO], **4**, was isolated, albeit in less yield. Although the compound was produced in a mixture, it could be separated by Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) which allowed spectroscopic and structural characterization of the pure material. Note that the above reaction also yielded some air and moisture sensitive compounds in low yields, which could not be isolated by chromatographic technique.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of rhodaborane **4**.

Compound **4** was isolated as a purple, relatively air stable solid in 4% yield. The mass spectrometric data shows a molecular ion peak at *m/z* 839.1726. The ¹¹B NMR spectrum at room showed four resonances at δ = 60.0, 29.9, 15.0, 2.6, -2.1 ppm in the ratio of 1:2:1:1:1. The ¹H NMR spectrum showed the presence of two types of Cp* in 1:2 ratio. Besides the BH terminal protons, two up-field resonances at δ = -2.87 and -13.59 ppm were also observed, which can be designated to the presence of B-H-B and Rh-H-B respectively. The characteristic bands for the terminal B-H protons were confirmed by using IR spectroscopy.

To confirm the spectroscopic assignments and to determine the crystal structure of **4**, the X-ray diffraction analysis was undertaken.

Compound **4** was crystallized in monoclinic crystal sys-

tem with space group *P*21/*n*. The molecular structure of **4** shown in Fig. 1, has a *nido* geometry which may be generated from a bi-capped square antiprism geometry (see Fig. 2). It has degree three, four and five vertices, in which all the rhodium atoms occupy degree five vertices. Unlike, in decaborane compound **4** has a Rh-Rh bond with a bond distance of 2.757 Å. The molecule has a mirror plane which passes through B1, Rh2, B6 and C31 atoms. All the boron atoms are connected to the terminal hydrogen atoms and the Cp* ligands were attached to each of the Rh vertices. The extra bridging hydrogens are expected to be located on the open six membered face. The average Rh-B bond length is slightly longer as-compared to other rhodaboranes,³³ whereas the B-B distances are in accord with reported rhodaboranes³³. The M-H-B in **4** could not be located by X-ray diffraction studies; however, their connectivity has been assertively determined by ¹H NMR spectroscopy. Compound **4** possess a total sep of 11, consistent with the skeletal electron count of *nido*-[B₉H₁₃] and thus obeys the Wade-Mingos rule for a *nido* system^{10,11}.

Fig. 1. Molecular structure and labeling diagram of **4**. Selected bond lengths (Å) and angles (°): B6-Rh4 2.118(10), B6-Rh1 2.109(9), B1-Rh2 2.049(10), B2-Rh2 2.154(10), B5-Rh1 2.294(10), B1-B5 1.843(16), B2-B3 1.821(14), C31-Rh1 1.994(9), C31-Rh4 2.001(9), Rh1-Rh4 2.7550(9); B5-B1-B2 99.7(7).

Fig. 2. Schematic generation of observed geometry of **4** from a bi-capped square antiprism by removing one 5 connect vertex. The red line represent the bonds breaking during the rearrangement.

Scheme 2. Synthesis of heterometallic carbonyl cluster **7**.

Synthesis of heterometallic metal carbonyl cluster **7**:

The reaction of *nido-1* with $[\text{Fe}_2(\text{CO})_9]$ gave compounds $[(\text{Cp}^*\text{Rh})_2\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_4\text{B}_3\text{H}_2\text{Cl}]$, **5** and $[(\text{Cp}^*\text{Rh})_2\text{Fe}_2(\text{CO})_7\text{B}_2\text{H}_2]$, **6** in moderate yields^{31b}. In addition, the reaction also generated a non-boron cluster, found to be a trigonal heterometallic carbonyl cluster, $[(\text{Cp}^*\text{Rh})\{\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_3\}\{\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_4\}(\mu\text{-CO})_2]$, **7** by a cluster degradation reaction (Scheme 2, Fig. 3). Note that

this reaction also yielded some air and moisture sensitive compounds in low yields, which could not be isolated by chromatographic technique.

The ^{11}B NMR spectrum did not show any ^{11}B chemical shifts even at low temperature. The composition of compound **7** was unequivocally established by spectroscopic techniques and X-ray crystallography. The metal-metal bond distances of **7** are consistent with the sum of their covalent radii of the respective metal atoms (Fe-Fe: 2.729 Å; Fe-Rh: 2.590 Å).

Fig. 3. Molecular structure and labelling diagram of **7**. Selected bond lengths (Å) and angles (°): Fe1-Rh1 2.5896(5), Fe1-Fe2 2.7290(8), Fe2-Rh1 2.6918(5), C11-Fe1 1.999(3), C11-O1 1.161(4), C12-Rh1 2.006(3); C11-Rh1-Fe2 85.03(9), C12-Rh1-Fe2 82.86(9), Fe1-Rh1-Fe2 62.190(15), Rh1-Fe2-Fe1 57.068(13), Rh1-Fe1-Fe2 60.742(15).

Conclusions

In this article we have described the synthesis of one metal-rich open cage metallaborane from the cluster expansion reaction of *nido-1* with metal carbonyl fragments. The reactivity pattern of *nido-1* towards different metal carbonyl compounds is different that has been reflected from the different product distribution. For example, while the reactivity of *nido-1* with $[\text{Mn}_2(\text{CO})_{10}]$ generates a rhodaborane, reactivity with $[\text{Fe}_2(\text{CO})_9]$ on the other hand led to the isolation heterometallic metallaborane clusters and a metal carbonyl compound. The isolation of $[(\text{Cp}^*\text{Rh})_3\text{B}_6\text{H}_8\text{CO}]$ is an important addition to the rhodaborane library.

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